

WORK ON SYSTEMATIC GRAMMATICAL TASKS AIMED AT CREATING TEXT

M.N.Sanoyeva

PhDNavoi City 12-IDUM

teacher of mother tongue and literature

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11281019>

Annotation: the article talks about the necessary methodological principles of teaching students to create text. The issues of comparing, differentiating, selecting, grouping, analyzing and synthesizing linguistic phenomena and preparing the younger generation for Text creation on the basis of interdisciplinary communication are widely covered.

Keywords: oral text, written text, integration, speech ability.

In teaching students to create text, the teacher in the lessons of the native language should demand from the student to repeatedly edit the text after its creation, to diligently think over each word, vocabulary, each sentence, to compact the redundancies and inappropriate details in the text, repeated classifications. Such an approach generates and strengthens the skills of creating text and methodically editing it in readers.

When teaching students to create text, the following methodological recommendations should be taken into account:

- taking into account the young psychology, speech skills and capabilities of students when creating a text;
- to build on the principle of learning the native language in interaction with other disciplines in the process of creating text;
- comparison, differentiation, selection, grouping, analysis and synthesis of language phenomena;
- addressing questions that increase reader sensitivity when creating text;
- development of oral and written speech on the principle of Science and intelligibility, continuity and continuity;
- as an addition to the textbook, the introduction of speech training exercises, problematic training tasks, psycholinguistic tests, exercises for drawing up control questions based on the topic and their continuous improvement.

Shu nuqtayi nazardan, 5–6-sinf o‘quvchilariga quyidagi grammatik topshiriqlar asosida matn yaratish tavsiya etiladi:

Task 1: "Write a greeting card". Base words: dear, honorable, priceless oaths, kindness, sincerely, your life path.

Task 2. Fill in the text by placing words corresponding to the content of the faces represented in the text. Continue with creative thoughts.

I became rosa 😊 today. You know, my mother came out of the hospital. I love them. Toblari is upset when he flees, and secretly 😞. It all ended with good 😊. Now it will be all 🖤 again. The Angel Of Our Lady returned home. 🙏 🙏 🙏 🙏 how good is jamuljamal - a.

Task 3. Make a text with the participation of the word flower.

Flower conversation (example of text composed by the reader)

The Rose, which is the canopy of a large garden, one day has a conversation with kashgargul. The Rose, counting herself a princess, bragged about the kashgargul:

-You can't find a beautiful flower in this mask from me. I also have a fragrant freshness again. Bulbul sings towards me. My community is compared to the girls ... (Sahatqulova adoration, 6th grade student)

Students in grades 7-8 were advised to formulate content, styles and forms of independent Text creation through the following aspects:

- determination of the exact purpose of the text being created;
- independent selection and justification of the text;
- development of a clear plan and program of the text;
- determination of forms and deadlines for self-control;
- expanding and deepening knowledge;
- generalization and conclusion of thoughts.

The reader's creation of text is associated with his ability to independently think. The capacity for independent thinking, on the other hand, is formed, above all, by its own reasoning, confidence and assessment capacity. The formation of critical thinking skills is also important in the development of text creation skills in students. A student with this characteristic is usually characterized by perseverance, clear planning of his activities and willingness to analyze and correct the mistakes he has made, being able to correctly assess the situation and not back down until he has achieved the goal. In this, such qualities as assessing one's behavior, understanding and applying intellectual methods and strategies, analyzing one's own shortcomings in cognitive activity and their causes and assessing their achievements, and looking for ways of compromise are necessary. For example, if students are instructed to create a text on the topic "opportunity is grief, King Lines-la, the moment of embellishment OMR daftin...", readers will have to be able to interpret the wisdom in the poetic verse from the text.

Fursat g'animatdir, shoh satrlar-la, Bezamoq onidir umr daftarin...

(example from the text created by the reader)

There is no exaggeration to say that this poem of the poet is a "monument to the moment". For a person who realizes, feels the eternal laws of life, there is no and cannot be a meaningless moment. After all, these moments form the basis of this life, no matter how many years a person lives.

Making the most of the opportunity given is in the hands of each of us. Therefore, it is necessary that we spend our time without wasting our knowledge from the cocoon. It is difficult for us to read and learn when necessary. (Eshmirzayeva Rukhshona, Uchkuduq district 10th School, 8th grade student)

In this methodological recommendation, students will be able to simultaneously develop the skills of reading, writing, commenting and speaking. Also, the selected text also instills the thinking of the reader's worldview. Due to its educational value, it is retained in the reader's memory, leading to an increase in vocabulary.

When creating a text based on the principle of studying the native language in interaction with other subjects, students' knowledge from the philological Sciences, Social, specific, natural, economic and Applied Educational Sciences is manifested.

The new edition of the native language textbook, designed for the 5th grade of general secondary education schools, reads: "Nature and US", "Allapinin", "the giant explosion", "the Polar Star", "the culture of talking on the phone", "Alpine land to the first", "Bridges", "What is the Constitution?", "Is there Intelligence in fish?", "Founder of the algorithm", "ancient cities" included texts on such subjects as history, mathematics, medicine, geography. We will not be mistaken if we say this is the first step to the emergence of requirements based on the holistic assimilation of the types of speech activities of the national program (listening, reading, speaking, writing), knowledge of the correct use of speech skills in all areas of communication.

In the 2022-2023 school year, the teaching of the native language was established on the basis of new textbooks based on the national curriculum for the 6th, 7th grades. The program includes text – based test questions, discussion topics, project work to improve the effectiveness of the study of texts given in chapters such as "Me, You, him and them", "favors of Nature", "healthy mind", "my profession – pride", "young economist", "Science and technology", "language and language", "treasures of History", "Art and culture", "our right". The aim of

this is to promote oratory competence and prepare students for international assessment systems such as PISA, PIRLS.

It is noteworthy that interdisciplinary integration is not only observed in the process of connecting mother tongue lessons with other subjects, but also in the process of learning other subjects in connection with the mother tongue. We will witness the task of “discuss” more on the topics in the textbook of Natural Sciences of the 6th grade, compiled on the basis of the national curriculum. For example, in the theme “animal life”, “most animals have organs of action. What organs of movement do you know of animals? For what purposes do animals move?” questions were put into discussion. On the basis of the knowledge gained, students talk about the animals they see in life or on television, the organs involved in their movement, the peculiarities and advantages of these organs. It is a product of oral speech, proving that the skills of following the word order in a sentence in the teaching of the native language, drawing up a narrative text, A Pictorial text are formed. When the same aspects are written based on the analysis of specific information, a small scientific text is created on its own.

This methodological recommendation creates conditions for the systematic development of speech skills in each student. In particular, the relevance of the selected text to global problems, as well as the influence of the information contained in it on the thinking of the reader, as well as the responsibility to teach animals to preserve, treat animals well.

The texts created as a result of interdisciplinary integration reflect the theoretical knowledge, scientific and creative observations that students receive from all disciplines. For Example: **Assignment. Create a text on the topic “Constitution – the basis of laws” using legal terms.**

Constitution-the basis of laws

Proudly and proudly, it can be said that all the reforms carried out in our country are directly based on the principle of the rule of law. The path to equality and justice in society was opened. The law is a means of exercising popular Power, Managing society, regulating social relations between the state and citizens. So, both the arms and protection of the legal state, and the shield, and the eye, are law... (Shakhriyeva Shakhina, 8th grade student)

It seems that the effective organization of interdisciplinary integration provides the basis for the free application of students' knowledge from various disciplines in written speech in the educational process. This approach, known today as STEAM, is a new method of teaching and is a different methodology

than the traditional method of teaching. The knowledge gained from these subjects helps students to become highly qualified professionals in the future. As a result, students try to acquire knowledge and immediately put them into practice.

The main didactic tool for giving knowledge at school is considered a textbook. Therefore, the theoretical information given in textbooks should be appropriate for the age and psychology of the student, formative of National thinking and ideology, and exercises and tasks should be modern and rich in information that can attract the student. Myths, narratives, wise words, parables, proverbs and sayings, which are incomparable examples of folk oral creativity, have served as a constant spiritual resource for students to create creative texts. When, using proverbs and sayings within the framework of a topic, the reader is instructed to create a text, readers quickly and easily cope with this task:

When speaking of word magic...

In our wise people,, there is a difference in the word from the word, there are thirty-two prices,' there is a purma'no proverb. Indeed, as they say,' the adornment of the House, the adornment of the word, the adornment of man", we can always know who man is, his worldview, what profession he represents from his spoken word. Of course,, decorate the ditch water, the man-the word"...(Godly charm, 8th grade student)

An interesting organization of classes makes it possible to quickly apply the grammatical Bkms acquired when creating text in the desired place. Instructing students to create text using words that start with one letter will create such a process. For example:

A man of Science-a possibility to humanity

Man is inquisitive. Looking for science and looking for the opportunity. Science. The wise man is a sign, the ignorant man isnod. The wise man is proud of science. In a learned person, creativity is expressed. Previously, the learned worked impossible, without privileges. Science - human Iqbal. Intentionality is the innermost self of a person. Inchunun, look for science.(Nuritdinov Shamshod, Karmana district 5th School, 8th grade student)

Educated boy-rich boy

We know that today the educated are wealthy. Knowledge-begins to happiness, wealth. Ignorance is from the scourge of indifference, apathy, indifference. The knowledgeable begumon is happy. Knowledge-wakefulness. Indulging in involuntary knowledge is happiness. Know how to be my

knowledgeable brother first. (Nabiyeva Purple, Gijduvon district 4th School, 8th grade student)

The task chosen in this methodological recommendation increases the possibility of teaching the reader through the text to strengthen their orthoepic and orthographic knowledge, while systematically developing skills for fluent speech, expressive reading, literate writing.

Text creation assignments relying on diagrams, tables, databases have become popular today in order to prepare students for international PIRLS and PISA studies. In this, students should thoroughly master information, find their similarities and differences in the desired place, create a text, summing up thoughts about their experiences or views.

In general, when teaching students to create text, the teacher in the lessons of his native language should require the reader to repeatedly edit the text after its creation, to diligently think over each word, vocabulary, each sentence, to compact the redundancies and inappropriate details in the text, repeated classifications. Such an approach generates and strengthens the skills of text creation and its methodological editing in readers.

References:

- 1.Yuldasheva D.N. Evolutionary progress of the goal of native language education– Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2013. – 168 b.
- 2.Ziyodova T. Text creation technology. - T.: Science, 2007. -155 b.
- 3.Ziyodova T. Talisman riddles-a factor in the formation of speech activity. (methodological guide for native language teachers). - Tashkent: RTM, 1999. – 73 b.
- 4.Ziyodova T. Teaching students to think independently. - Tashkent: RTM, 2000. – 163 b.
- 5.Ziyomammedov B., Tojiev M. Pedagogical technology is a modern Uzbek model. Methodical guide. - Tashkent: Leader Press, 2009. – 42-43.
- 6.Gulomov A., Ne'matov H. Content of native language education. Manual for native language teachers. - T.: Teacher, 1995. – 128 b.
- 7.Gulomov A., Kabylova B. Speech cultivation training. Methodical guide for teachers. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1995. – 160 b.

